

Synthesis of Furano Compounds : Part XXXIV. Wanzlick Oxidation of 3-Hydroxycoumarins*

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Wanzlick oxidative coupling¹ of catechol with 3-hydroxycoumarin and its derivatives has been studied and it is shown that coumarino(3', 4'-2, 3)-coumarones are formed. The derived quinones such as (VII) are readily synthesised from 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone and 3-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin. A synthesis of coumarino (3', 4'-2, 3) coumarone (termed as *iso*-coumestan) is also reported.

Wanzlick *et al.*¹ carried out the oxidative coupling of catechol with 4-hydroxycoumarins to give coumarino (3', 4'-3, 2) coumarones and they succeeded to synthesise *o*-trimethylwedelolactone by a short and efficient biogenetically important procedure. As an extension of this important work, we have coupled 3-hydroxycoumarin with catechol in presence of potassium ferricyanide to give an excellent yield of 5, 6-dihydroxycoumarino (3' 4'-2, 3)-coumarone (I) which was characterised by the preparation of the diacetate (III) and the dimethyl ether (II) (IR absorption at 1730 cm⁻¹). In a similar manner, 3-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin^{2,3} was oxidatively coupled with catechol to give (IV) in good yield which was methylated to (V). The latter has been synthesised in the conventional manner⁴ from methyl 2-hydroxy-4, 5-dimethoxybenzoate as shown below :

* A preliminary account appeared in Tetrahedron Letters, 1969, 3337.

1. H. W. Wanzlick, R. Gritzky and H. Heideprien, *Chem. Ber.*, 1963, **96**, 305.
2. H. A. Offe and H. Jatazkewitz, *Chem. Ber.*, 1947, **80**, 474.
3. J. N. Chatterjea, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957 **34**, 304.

Thus, methyl 2-hydroxy-4, 5-dimethoxybenzoate was condensed with ethyl bromoacetate to obtain ethyl (2-methoxycarbonyl-4, 5-dimethoxy)phenoxyacetate. The latter, on Dieckmann condensation gave the ethyl 5, 6-dimethoxycoumaran-3-one-2-carboxylate which on Pechmann condensation with resorcinol and subsequent methylation of the resulting 5, 6-dimethoxy-7'-hydroxycoumarino (3', 4'-2, 3) coumarone gave (V).

3-Hydroxycoumarin also reacted smoothly with 2, 3-dichloro-1, 4-naphtho-quinone (cf. Buu-Ho'i⁵) to give the quinone (VI) in excellent yield. The quinone has been reductively acetylated to give (VIII). To establish the structure of the quinone, 3-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin was condensed with 2, 3-dichloro-1, 4-naphthoquinone to give the quinone (VII) which was characterised by reductive acetylation to (IX). This quinone was secured unambiguously from ethyl benzo(5, 6)coumaran-3-one-2-carboxylate⁶ which on Pechmann condensation with resorcinol gave (X). This was methylated and oxidised by chromic acid to (VII), identical with the specimen obtained by the previous route.

It may be mentioned that the parent coumarino (3', 4'-2, 3)coumarone (XVI) (which may be termed as *iso*-coumestan) has not yet been synthesised. This has now been prepared from ω -phenoxy-*o*-methoxyacetophenone (XII), which on cyclodehydration with phosphoric anhydride in benzene gave 3-*o*-methoxyphenyl-coumarone (XIII). This was formylated to the aldehyde (XIV) in *o*-dichlorobenzene with NN-dimethylformamide and phosphorus

4. H. I. King, R. H. Holland, F. P. Reed and A. Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1672.
5. N. P. Buu-Ho'i, J. P. Hoefflinger and P. Jacquignon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 6105.
6. Hoechst a.M., *Chemisches Zentral-Blatt*, 1900(I), 495.

oxychloride and then oxidised by silver hydroxide to the acid (XV). The acid on demethylation afforded *iso*-oumestan (XVI).

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.ps. and b p.s. are uncorrected.

5, 6-Dihydroxycoumarino(3', 4'-2, 3)coumarone (I): To a solution of 3-hydroxycoumarin (1.62 g.) and catechol (1.10 g.) in acetone (100 ml.) and water (15 ml.) was added slowly in one hour with stirring, a solution of potassium ferricyanide (8.89 g.) and crystalline sodium acetate (7.78 g.) in water (67 ml.). 5, 6-Dihydroxycoumarino (3', 4'-2, 3) coumarone (I) begins to separate during the addition. After complete addition of potassium ferricyanide solution, stirring was continued for further one hour and then heated on water bath to remove acetone. The mixture was cooled, filtered and the residue was washed with warm water. The dihydroxy compound was obtained as a dark powder (1.5 g.).

5, 6-Dimethoxycoumarino (3', 4'-2, 3) coumarone (II): The above dihydroxy compound (I : 0.2 g.) was methylated by refluxing for 10 hrs. with methyl iodide and anhydrous K_2CO_3 in dry acetone. On working up, the *furo-coumarin*(II; 0.1 g.) was obtained which crystallised from acetic acid in long bars, m.p. 291-2°. (Found : C, 68.56; H, 4.47. $C_{17}H_{12}O_5$ requires : C, 68.91; H, 4.08%). IR spectrum; 1730 cm^{-1} (Lactone carbonyl).

5, 6-Diacetoxycoumarino(3', 4'-2, 3)coumarone (III): The foregoing dihydroxy compound (I) was treated with acetic anhydride in dry pyridine and left overnight. On working up as usual, the acetyl derivative was crystallised from acetic acid, using charcoal, m.p. 247-8°. (Found : C, 64.51; H, 3.87. $C_{19}H_{12}O_7$ requires : C, 64.77; H, 3.43%).

5, 6-Dihydroxy-7'-methoxycoumarino(3', 4'-2, 3)coumarone (IV): (*cf.* I) To a solution of 3-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin^{2,3} (1.6 g.) and catechol (0.92 g.) in acetone (100 ml.) and water (15 ml.) was added slowly during one hour with stirring, a solution of potassium ferricyanide (7.44 g.) and crystalline sodium acetate (6.48 g.) in water (55 ml.). On working up, the dihydroxy compound (IV; 1.6 g.) was obtained as a dark powder.

5, 6, 7'-*Trimethoxycoumarino* (3', 4'-2, 3) *coumarone* (V) : The methylation was done as before (cf. II). The *furo-coumarin* (V) was obtained as needles from acetic acid, m.p. 268-70°. (Found : C, 65.86; H, 4.61. $C_{13}H_{14}O_6$ requires : C, 66.25; H, 4.32%).

3, 4-*Dimethoxyphenol* : Acetoveratrone (60 g.) was dissolved in peracetic acid (250 ml.; 7%) and kept at room temperature for 24 hrs. A fresh quantity of peracetic acid (320 ml.) was added in two lots during another 24 hrs. with intermittent shaking and slightly warming the contents. Peracetic acid was then removed on water bath under reduced pressure and the remaining liquid distilled at 130°/2.25 mm. The viscous liquid distillate (55 g.) was then hydrolysed by refluxing it with aqueous potassium hydroxide (200 ml.; 20%) for 4 hrs. Acidification of the resulting solution with hydrochloric acid gave an oil which solidified on cooling. It was filtered and purified by distillation under reduced pressure followed by crystallisation from chloroform (40 g.), m.p. 71°.

2-*Hydroxy-4, 5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde* : It was prepared by the method of Head and Robertson⁷ with a slight modification. Hydrogen chloride was led into a suspension of 3, 4-dimethoxyphenol (15 g.) and zinc cyanide (30 g.) in dry ether (200 ml.). A brown double zinc salt separated during the course of saturation. On working up⁷ (after 12 hr.), the aldehyde (15 g.) was separated as crystalline mass. Recrystallisation from aqueous alcohol and then from methanol gave colourless rhombic plates, m.p. 106° (lit.⁷, m.p. 105°).

Methyl 2-hydroxy-4, 5-dimethoxybenzoate : 2-Hydroxy-4, 5-dimethoxybenzoic acid was prepared from the above aldehyde⁸. The acid was esterified by refluxing with methanol and conc. sulphuric acid. The methyl ester was crystallised from water as colourless needles, m.p. 99°.

Ethyl 2-methoxycarbonyl-4, 5-dimethoxyphenoxyacetate : A mixture of the above ester (3.5 g.), potassium carbonate (10 g.) and ethyl bromoacetate (3.3 g.) in dry acetone (60 ml.) was refluxed for 12 hr. The acetone solution was evaporated and the solid residue crystallised from petroleum ether (60-80°) to give white woolly needles (5.7 g.), m.p. 87°. (Found : C, 56.72; H, 6.54. $C_{14}H_{18}O_7$ requires : C, 56.37; H, 6.04 %).

Ethyl 5, 6-dimethoxycoumaran-3-one-2-carboxylate : A mixture of the above di-ester (2 g.) and powdered sodium (0.3 g.) was taken in toluene (30 ml.) and heated on water bath for 12 hr. The brown sodium salt separated was dissolved by adding cold water and the aqueous layer was separated, washed with ether and acidified with hydrochloric acid to get a brown mass which on crystallisation from ethanol afforded colourless needles (1.1 g.), m.p. 144-5°. The compound gives a violet colour with ferric chloride. (Found : C, 58.09; H, 5.25. $C_{13}H_{14}O_6$ requires : C, 58.60; H, 5.26%). IR spectrum : 1675 cm^{-1} (keto).

5, 6-*Dimethoxy-7'-hydroxycoumarino* (3', 4'-2, 3)*coumarone* : A suspension of ethyl 5, 6-dimethoxycoumaran-3-one-2-carboxylate (0.6 g.) and resorcinol (1 g.) in methanol (2 ml.) was saturated with hydrogen chloride gas in the cold and the mixture left at room temp.

7. F. S. H. Head and A. Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2434.

8. F. S. H. Head and A. Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2432.

9. S. Senoh and T. Sakan, *J. Chem. Soc. Japan*, (Pure Chem. Section), **74**, 733-5.

for 2 days. The resulting brown solid was filtered and washed with a little methanol. The crude solid (0.5 g.) melted at 310°. IR spectrum : 1730 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl).

5, 6, 7'-*Trimethoxycoumarino* (3', 4'-2, 3) *coumarone* (V) : The above hydroxy compound (0.1 g.) was dissolved in minimum quantity of 1% sodium hydroxide solution at room temp. and to this was added 1 ml. of dimethyl sulphate. The mixture was vigorously stirred and a 5% solution of sodium hydroxide added dropwise till the solution became faintly alkaline. The precipitated methyl derivative, after further agitation for half an hour, was filtered, washed and recrystallised from acetic acid (0.1 g.), m.p. 266-7°. The i.r. spectrum was superimposable with Wanzlick oxidation product. The 5, 6-dimethoxy-7'-hydroxycoumarino (3', 4'-2,3) coumarone could not be methylated with methyl iodide and potassium carbonate in acetone satisfactorily.

This compound was also prepared directly by Pechmann condensation of ethyl 5, 6-dimethoxycoumarone-3-one-2-carboxylate with resorcinol monomethylether.

5, 6-Dimethoxy-7'-*acetoxy*coumarino(3', 4'-2, 3)*coumarone* : The foregoing hydroxy compound was acetylated as before. The acetylated compound was crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles, m.p. 295-6°. IR spectrum : 1725 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl), 1760 cm^{-1} (acetoxy carbonyl) and 1240 cm^{-1} (-O—CO—bending frequency).

Coumarino(3', 4'-2, 3)-*benzo*(5, 6)-4, 7-*dioxocoumarone* (VI) : 3-Hydroxy-coumarin (0.8 g.) and 2, 3-dichloro-1, 4-naphthoquinone (1.3 g.) were taken in dry pyridine (8 ml.), and a drop of piperidine was added to the mixture. The mixture was refluxed for 5 hr. with exclusion of moisture. The product which separated as solid (0.81 g.) was collected by filtration and washed with water. Crystallisation from acetic acid afforded dirty green prismatic short needles, m.p. 281-1.5°. It develops an orange colour in conc. sulphuric acid. (Found : C, 71.90; H, 2.70. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_8\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 72.14; H, 2.55%).

Coumarino(3', 4'-2, 3)-*benzo*(5, 6)-4, 7-*diacetoxy*coumarone (VIII) : A mixture of the quinone (VI; 0.1 g.), zinc dust (0.08 g.), acetic anhydride (3.2 ml.) and fused sodium acetate (0.32 g.) was refluxed for 3 hr. The colourless solution was added to water and the residual zinc extracted with small quantities of acetic acid which were added to water. The precipitate of the di-acetate was collected, crystallised from acetic acid in elongated blades (0.09 g.), m.p. 269-71°. (Found : C, 68.30; H, 3.70. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_7$ requires : C, 68.66; H, 3.51%).

7'-*Methoxycoumarino*(3', 4'-2, 3)-*benzo*(5, 6)-4, 7-*dioxocoumarone* (VII) : (cf. prepn. VI) A mixture of 3-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin (0.2 g.), 2, 3-dichloro-1, 4-naphthoquinone (0.236 g.), dry pyridine (7 ml.) and a drop of piperidine was refluxed for 8 hr. On working up, the crude quinone (VII; 0.21 g.) was obtained. It was sublimed at 325-30° (bath temp.) and 1 mm pressure, and crystallised from acetic acid in red prismatic needles, m.p. 330-1°. (Found : C, 69.57; H, 3.05. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6$ requires : C, 69.37; H, 2.91%). The quinone develops an orange colour in conc. sulphuric acid.

7'-*Methoxycoumarino*(3', 4'-2, 3)-*benzo*(5, 6)-4, 7-*diacetoxy*coumarone (IX) : The quinone (VII; 0.1 g.) was reductively acetylated as before (cf. prepn. VIII). The diacetate (IX; 0.1 g.) was collected and crystallised from acetic acid in elongated blades, m.p. 277-8°. (Found : C, 66.15; H, 3.89. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_8$ requires : C, 66.67; H, 3.73%).

7'-Hydroxycoumarino(3', 4'-2, 3)-benzo(5, 6)coumarone (X): A suspension of ethyl benzo(5, 6)coumaran-3-one-2-carboxylate⁶ (0.51 g.) and resorcinol (0.724 g.) in dry methanol (6 ml.) was saturated with hydrogen chloride at about 0° and left overnight in refrigerator. The separated solid (0.6 g.) was collected, washed with a little methanol and dried. It gave a bright yellow sodium salt.

7'-Methoxycoumarino(3', 4'-2, 3)-benzo(5, 6) coumarone (XI): The hydroxy compound (X; 0.6 g.) was methylated by the process adopted in (II). The *furo-coumarin* (XI; 0.5g) was obtained which crystallised from acetic acid in long bars, m.p. 253-4°. (Found: C, 76.25; H, 4.15. C₂₀H₁₂O₄ requires: C, 75.94; H, 3.82%). IR spectrum: 1729 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl).

7'-Acetoxycoumarino(3', 4'-2, 3)-benzo(5, 6)coumarone: The *furo-coumarin* (X) was acetylated as before. The acetylated compound was crystallised from acetic acid in plates, m.p. 285-6°. (Found: C, 72.88; H, 3.91. C₂₁H₁₂O₅ requires: C, 73.25; H, 3.51%).

7'-Methoxycoumarino(3', 4'-2, 3)-benzo(5, 6)-4, 7-dioxocoumarone (VII): A solution of (XI; 0.316 g.) in acetic acid (5 ml.) was boiled under reflux and to this a solution of chromium trioxide (0.356 g.) in water (1.0 ml.) and acetic acid (3 ml.) was added in half an hour. The refluxing was continued for further 1 hr. The solution along with the solid was diluted with a little water and separated solid was collected, and dried. The crude quinone (0.29 g.) was sublimed at 325-30° (bath temp.) and 1 mm pressure. It crystallised from acetic acid in prismatic short needles, m.p. 329-30°. (Found: C, 69.60; H, 3.02. C₂₀H₁₀O₆ requires: C, 69.37; H, 2.91%). It develops an orange colour in conc. sulphuric acid. It was found identical when compared with the previous preparation (mixed m.p. and superimposable i.r. spectra).

7'-Methoxycoumarino(3', 4'-2, 3)-benzo(5, 6)-4, 7-diacetoxycoumarone (IX): The quinone (VII) obtained by chromic acid oxidation of (XI) was also reductively acetylated as before. The diacetate was crystallised from acetic acid in elongated blades, m.p. 276-8°. (Found: C, 66.76; H, 4.01. C₂₄H₁₆O₈ requires: C, 66.67; H, 3.73%).

ω-Phenoxy-o-methoxyacetophenone (XII): Phenol (4.4 g.), ω-bromo-o-methoxyacetophenone⁹ (10 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (15 g.) and dry acetone (60 ml.) were refluxed for 10 hr. The residue obtained on removal of acetone was taken up in ether, ethereal solution was washed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%), water and dried (MgSO₄). Removal of solvent furnishes the *ketone* (XII) which was distilled at 184.6°/2 mm and crystallised from alcohol in white, short needles (9 g.), m.p. 51-2°. (Found: C, 74.13; H, 5.57. C₁₅H₁₄O₃ requires: C, 74.36; H, 5.83%).

The ketone (XII) readily gave 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, crystallising as bright red needles from ethyl acetate, m.p. 186-7°. (Found: N, 13.50. C₂₁H₁₈O₆N₄ requires: N, 13.27%).

3-o-Methoxyphenylcoumarone (XIII): A solution of the above ketone (XII; 5 g.) in thiophene free dry benzene (100 ml), and phosphorus pentoxide (15 g.) were refluxed for 70 hr. The reaction product was decomposed with ice water. The benzene layer was separated and the extract of the aqueous layer mixed with it and dried (MgSO₄). The solvent was

removed and the residue was crystallised from alcohol in rectangular bars (XIII; 2.2 g.), m.p. 82-3°. (Found : C, 79.90; H, 5.20. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2$ requires : C, 80.33; H, 5.39%).

2-Formyl-3-(o-methoxyphenyl)coumarone (XIV) : 3-*o*-Methoxyphenylcoumarone (XIII; 2.24 g.) (dissolved in freshly distilled *o*-dichlorobenzene) was mixed with *N,N*-dimethylformamide (1.1 ml.) and cooled in iced water. To this solution, phosphorus oxychloride (1.4 ml.) was added dropwise with stirring. The mixture was then allowed to attain room temp. and was then heated in oil bath at 90-3° for 18 hr. The reaction product was cooled, basified with aqueous sodium hydroxide (10%), extracted with ether and the ether layer was washed with water. Ether was distilled off and *o*-dichlorobenzene was removed by steam distillation. The residue (2.1 g.) on crystallisation from methanol afforded the *aldehyde* (XIV) in needles, m.p. 92-3°. (Found : C, 75.81; H, 5.05. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires : C, 76.18; H, 4.80%).

The aldehyde (XIV) readily gave 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, crystallising as bright red needles from acetic acid, m.p. 289-91°. Found : N, 13.13. $C_{22}H_{16}O_4N_6$ requires : N, 12.96%).

*3-*o*-Methoxyphenylcoumarone-2-carboxylic acid (XV)* : The above aldehyde (XIV; 2.5 g.) and silver nitrate solution (3.4 g. in 42.5 ml. water) were boiled under reflux. To this boiling mixture, sodium hydroxide solution (1.3 g. in 9 ml. water) was added dropwise in about half an hour. The refluxing was continued till the silver mirror formed disintegrated. The solution was filtered hot. The filtrate on acidification with conc. hydrochloric acid gave the acid (XV; 2.2 g.) which crystallised from aqueous acetic acid in straw yellow long needles, m.p. 213-4°. (Found : C, 71.58; H, 4.80. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires : C, 71.63; H, 4.51%).

Coumarino(3',4'-2,3)coumarone (isocoumestan) (XVI) : The above acid (XV; 1 g.) was refluxed with acetic acid (8 ml.) and constant boiling hydrobromic acid (8 ml.) for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into cold water. It was extracted with ether. The ether layer was first washed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%) and then with water, and finally dried ($MgSO_4$). The residue (0.2 g.) obtained after removal of ether, was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 71-2°. (Found : C, 76.79; H, 3.50. $C_{15}H_8O_3$ requires : C, 76.20; H, 3.41%). IR spectrum : 1740 cm^{-1} (carbonyl absorption).

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